

**PROFITABILITY AND DETERMINANTS OF SYSTEM OF RICE
INTENSIFICATION TECHNOLOGY USAGE AMONG RICE FARMERS IN NIGER
STATE, NIGERIA**

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ARTICLE TYPE: Research Articles

ÖZET

Nijerya'da pirinç (*Oryza sativa*), yemek kasesinin ana bileşeni ve temel bir mahsuldür. Ülkedeki pirincin çoğu geleneksel yöntemlerle üretiliyor. Bu yöntem, pirinç üretim fiyatını yükseltti ve çiftçilerin tam üretim kapasitesine ulaşmasını zorlaştırdı. Geleneksel yaklaşımın yüksek maliyetine karşı koymak için, pirinç yetiştirme endüstrisinde Pirinç Yoğunlaştırma Sistemi (SRI) oluşturuldu. SRI teknolojisinin mali uygulanabilirliği ve Nijerya'da çiftçilerin bu teknolojiyi kullanmasını etkileyen değişkenler üzerine araştırma eksiktir. Bu nedenle, bu çalışma Nijerya'nın Nijer eyaletindeki pirinç çiftçileri arasında pirinç yoğunlaştırma teknolojisi kullanımının karlılığını ve belirleyicilerini inceledi. SRI teknolojisini kullanan 180 pirinç çiftçisini örneklemek için çok aşamalı örnekleme tekniği kullanıldı, çalışma için anket ve görüşme çizelgesi kullanıldı. Verilerin analizinde tanımlayıcı istatistikler brüt marj ve çok değişkenli regresyon kullanılmıştır. Çalışma, Nijer Eyaletinde SRI teknolojisini kullanan pirinç çiftçilerinin çoğunun 31 ila 40 yaşları arasındaki erkekler olduğunu keşfetti. Maliyet ve getiri analizinden elde edilen 0,40 karlılık indeksi, çalışma alanındaki çeltik tarımında SRI teknolojisinin kullanımının karlı olduğunu

göstergesidir. Çalışma alanında SRI kullanımının belirleyicilerine yönelik çok değişkenli analizin sonucu, yayım hizmetlerinin mevcudiyetinin ($P < 0.01$) transplantasyon teknolojisinin kullanımını olumlu yönde etkilediğini ortaya koydu. Çalışma, daha yeni pirinç çeşitleri geliştirmek ve kullanımlarını teşvik etmek için bilgi alışverişine, yayım demolarına ve çiftçilerin çalışmalara ve eğitim programlarına katılımına daha fazla önem verilmesini önerdi.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Pirinç, Pirinç yoğunlaştırma teknolojisi sistemi, kullanımı, karlılığı

ABSTRACT

In Nigeria, rice (*Oryza sativa*) is the main component of the food bowl and a staple crop. The majority of the nation's rice is produced using traditional methods. This method has driven up the price of producing rice and made it more difficult for farmers to reach their full output capacity. To counteract the high expense of the traditional approach, the System of Rice Intensification (SRI) was created in the rice growing industry. The research on the financial viability of SRI technology and the variables affecting farmers' use of it in Nigeria is lacking. Therefore, this study examined the profitability and determinants of the system of rice intensification technology usage among rice farmers in Niger state, Nigeria. Multi-stage sampling technique was used to sample 180 rice farmers using the SRI technology, questionnaire, and interview schedule were used for the study. Descriptive statistics gross margin and multivariate regression were employed in the analysis of data. The study discovered that most of the rice farmers using SRI technology in Niger State were males between the ages of 31 and 40 years. The profitability index of 0.40 from the costs and returns analysis is indicative of the fact that the use of SRI technology in rice farming in the study area is profitable. The result of the multivariate analysis for the determinants of the use of SRI in the study area revealed that the availability of extension services ($P < 0.01$) positively influenced the use of transplanting technology. The study recommended, to develop newer rice varieties and promote their use, more emphasis must be placed on knowledge exchange, extension demos, and farmers' participation in studies and training programs.

Keywords: Rice, System of rice intensification technology, usage, profitability.

1. INTRODUCTION

One-third of the world's total cereal plants are rice (*Oryza sativa*), which also supplies 35 to 60% of the calorie consumed by the world's 2.7 billion inhabitants (Tayefe, et al., 2014). According to Kirby (2017), roughly 500 million metric tons of rice are produced annually on an estimated 160 million hectares of land worldwide. Over 174 million people live in Nigeria, and its consumption has increased dramatically at a rate of roughly 10% per year. It is the most popular basic meal consumed across the country's geopolitical zones (Terwase & Madu, 2014).

Marginal farmlands with land endowments dispersing across various parcels define Nigeria's agricultural sector. This makes it more difficult for smallholders to raise output, make money, and enhance their living conditions. Farmers divide their parcels into portions to accommodate a wide range of preferences (Gauchan et al., 2012). Omofonmwan and Kadiri (2017) asserted that Nigeria's output of rice is imbalanced relative to the country's consumption habits. The disparity between supply and demand for rice will keep growing as both the population and the amount consumed rise (Abdul Fatah, & von Cramon-Taubadel 2017). The nation's dependence on rice imports is a result of the inability to produce enough rice on its own.

Nigeria's agricultural productivity is significantly influenced by the Niger state, and even though the State is a significant area with extensive tracts of land and the third-largest producer of rice in the country, relatively little has been done over the years to analyze its local rice production patterns, quantify yield potentials, and create new models for enhanced decision-making (Merem et al., 2017). Denkyirah (2015) stated that alternative water-saving methods should be used to improve sustainable rice production because the need for irrigation water in Nigeria surpasses the available water for rice irrigation.

There are several ways to cut back on the number of farm inputs necessary to produce rice (Ndiiri et al., 2013). Sudeep (2011) lists the Green Revolution, which includes several studies and transfer programs, as one of the most tested techniques. The Green Revolution entailed the

creation of cereal grain varieties with a high yield and the advancement of agricultural management practices (Rahman 2017). In Asia, where the idea proved successful, farmers embraced the technique (Ehiakpor et al., 2017; Thakur et al., 2015). Ndiiri et al. (2013) claim that the lack of adequate infrastructure and funding was the main reason why the Green Revolution was unable to assist several African nations.

Fernandes and Uphoff (2002) described the system of rice intensification (SRI) as a mechanism for boosting the production of irrigated rice by modifying the handling of plants, soil, water, nutrients, and replanting seeds and seedlings at a wider spacing. The method was created in the 1980s and has been claimed to offer a way to reduce water usage while retaining good yields. According to Thura (2010), the major components of SRI are water management, planting methods that include spacing arrangements, weed control, and soil fertility management.

SRI, according to Dobermann (2004), is a concept that involves manipulating the development conditions of rice seedlings, by enhancing plant, soil, water, and fertilizer management to encourage the formation of larger and richer root systems, as well as increasing the quantity and activity of advantageous soil fauna. SRI is gaining popularity around the world because farmers can cultivate additional rice with far less water, and a lower incidence of pests and illnesses than the traditional approach (Sudeep 2011).

Despite the various benefits of SRI technology, its usage in the state remains limited because of high input prices and labour expenses. Different cultivation processes, like SRI, have not yet been thoroughly examined, particularly in terms of their application. Previous research, such as Ndiiri et al. (2013), centered on the restrictions and revenues related to SRI, but the current study (Ndirangu 2015) concentrated on SRI perceptions. Little research has been conducted on the factors that influence SRI usage in Niger state. Furthermore, farmers confront several challenges while implementing the SRI approach. So, with effective diagnosis and removal of these problems, rice farming might be lucrative for farmers due to the higher yield per unit area.

Thus, this study examined the profitability and determinants of the system of rice intensification technology usage among rice farmers in Niger state, Nigeria. Specifically, it described the features of the socioeconomic status of the rice farmers in the study area, estimated the costs and returns to rice farmers using SRI technology in the study area, and identified the factors influencing the use of SRI technology by rice farmers in the study area.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Area

This research was conducted in Niger State, Nigeria. The state is located in Nigeria's middle belt. It is the biggest of the 36 states that make up the nation, taking up a tenth of its total land area. The state is located in Nigeria's Guinea Savannah (NGS) agroecological zone, with an average annual temperature of around 27 °C and precipitation ranging from 782-1250 mm (Iloeje, 2001). Tourist attractions such as the Gurara Waterfalls may be found in the state, as well as protected areas such as the Foge Islands and the Kainji Lake National Park, which include plants such as the Shea butter tree (*Vitellaria paradoxa*) and the African locust bean (*Parkia biglobosa*). The state is structured into 25 Local Government Areas (LGAs) (Alhaji et al., 2018). Niger State contains three agro-geographical zones, each with specific climatic features and agricultural techniques (Alhaji et al., 2018). Based on the National Bureau of Statistics (NBC, 2017), the state's population in 2016 was over 5550,000 people. The majority of the people live in rural areas and cultivate food crops such as yam (Iloeje, 2001). They also rear animals such as cattle and small ruminants. Its inhabitants are made up of many ethnic

groups, including the majority of Nupes, Gwaris, Kamaris, Bisasan, and Fulani herdsmen who live in nomadic tribes.

2.2 Sampling Procedures and Sample Size

The respondents were chosen using the multi-stage sampling approach. Firstly, two of Niger state's three agro-geographical zones were selected for the study and the list of rice producers was retrieved from the Niger Agricultural Development Project ADP in the second stage. The study's sampling frame was a list of rice producers retrieved from Niger ADP. A total sample size of 180 rice farmers was selected at random and a structured questionnaire was used to gather relevant data from the rice farmers on the list in Niger state.

2.3.0 Method of Data Analysis

The study's data were examined using descriptive statistics such as tables, frequency, percentages, gross margin, and Multivariate Regression.

2.3.1 Gross Margin

Cost and returns analysis was used to estimate the costs and returns to rice farmers using SRI technology in the study area. This includes calculating the respondents' gross margin, revenue on farm management, labour, and capital employed. The gross margin is the difference between the total variable cost and the gross value of agricultural production (Gross Farm Income, GFI) (TVC). It is a valuable tool for planning in instances when fixed capital is an aspect of farming operations.

$$GM = GFI - TVC$$

Where;

GFI = Gross Farm Income, GM = Gross Margin, TVC = Total Variable Cost.

The profitability index is indicative of an enterprise's capacity to turn a profit. In this study, profitability was assessed by adding rice revenues and subtracting production expenses. The cost-benefit ratio was determined by dividing the net return by the aggregate cost to get the estimated present profit from SRI. The equation used for calculating the benefit costs ratio is:

$$\sum \left\{ \frac{Rn}{(1+r)^n} \right\} \left\{ \frac{Cn}{(1+r)^n} \right\}$$

where: r = interest rate, R = revenue, n = number of years, C = costs.

2.3.2 Multivariate Regression

To describe discrete choices such as the adoption of new technology, single probit, and logit models are widely used. These models, however, are insufficient for dealing with the simultaneous application of various technologies. Multivariate models, such as multinomial logit models, are commonly used to assess choices regarding interdependent options. The multinomial Logistic model (MNL) was used to identify the factors influencing the use of SRI technology by the farmers in the study area. This study adapted MNL in line with Yirga and Hassan (2008) who used multinomial logit to model interdependent soil fertility and soil conservation adoption decisions.

Rice farmers were classed as either user with a value of one or non-users with a value of zero (Ghimire et al., 2015). Farmers that employ SRI can have their probability function expressed as a latent variable expression of the observed independent variable, x_i , and an error term ε_i :

$$y_1^* = x_i' \beta + \varepsilon_i \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

SRI users can be defined in two ways: yes, $y=1$, no, $y=0$; the likelihood of $y=1$ is expressed as shown in the equation below (2):

$$P_r(y_i = 1|x_i) = G(x_i\beta) \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

A function having two outcomes, zero or one, can be written as follows:

$$P_r(Users = 1) = G(\beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \dots + \beta_kX_k + \varepsilon) \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

(User = 1) Given the predictor variables x_1, \dots, x_k , this function calculates the farmer's likelihood of utilizing SRI. The intercept is denoted by β_0 , while the estimated parameters for the predictor variables are denoted by β_1, \dots, β_k , with ε being the error term:

$$G(z) = \frac{\exp(z)}{1+\exp(z)} \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

The explanatory factors were the farming experience of the rice farmers (X_1), association membership of the rice farmers (X_2), household size (X_3), educational level (X_4), and extension service (X_5).

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Socio-economic Characteristics of the Rice Farmers in the Study Area

Table 1: Socio-economic characteristics of the rice farmers in the Study Area

Socio-economic variable	Measurement	Mean distribution
Sex	Dummy (1, "Male"; 0, otherwise)	1.0
Age	Years	40.8
Household Size	Persons	7.6
Rice Farming Experience	Years	15.7
Level of Education	Dummy (1, "Formal Education"; 0, otherwise)	0.99
Cooperative Membership	Dummy (1, "Membership"; 0, otherwise)	0.94

Source: Field survey, 2022.

Table 1 shows the socioeconomic features of the rice farmers in the study area. The result showed the mean sex and household size of the rice farmers as 1.0 and 7.6, respectively. This implied that all of the rice farmers were men, with a mean age of approximately 41 years, and has approximately 8 persons in their household. The implication of this is that most of the rice farmers in the study area are 41 years. Individuals of this age group are economically productive, according to Otitoju et al., (2022). The productivity among these farmers could as a result of using new technologies like SRI to boost their output.

The average year of rice farming experience is around 16 years, meaning that the majority of rice farmers have been in the business for about 16 years. According to Nwaobiala (2014), when a farmer gains expertise, he or she becomes less scared of the hazards connected with implementing new technology such as SRI.

Furthermore, the Table revealed that 99% of the farmers had formal education. Formal education is critical in agriculture because it may lead to the employment of innovative agricultural practices such as SRI, which has the potential to increase farmers' profitability sustainably. 94% of rice farmers are members of one or more cooperative societies. Cooperative membership provides farmers with access to loans, knowledge, and a variety of other inputs that may be advantageous to their farming activity.

3.2 The Profitability of SRI Technology in the Study area

Table 2: Cost and Returns of rice farmers using SRI technology in the Study Area

Items	Amount (N/Ha)	Percentage
A Total revenue		
Sales from produced rice	387,149	100
B Variable cost		
Cost of seeds	15,000	6.52
Cost of transportation	5,600	2.43
Fertilizer	78,456	34.09
Herbicide	20,304	8.82
Labour	110,789	48.14
Total variable cost	230,149	100
C Total cost	230,149	
Gross Margin (TR-TVC)	157,000	
Profitability index	0.40	

Source; Field Survey 2022.

Table 2, shows the outcome of the costs and returns analysis on rice production in the study area. From table 2, it was observed that labour cost (48.14%) constituted a larger portion of the total variable cost, this was followed by fertilizer (34.09%), herbicide (8.82%), cost of seeds (6.52%) and transportation cost (2.43%). This could be attributed to the fact that labour use is more intensive when using SRI technology. This finding is consistent with Das et al. (2016), who found that farmers encountered significant labour costs because the SRI approach needed more labour per hectare than the conventional method. Table 2, also reveals a total cost of ₦230,149 and a total income of ₦387,149. The gross margin (GM) is ₦157,000 which implies that the SRI farmers made a profit of ₦157,000 over variable costs. The profitability index of 0.40 is indicative of the fact that the use of SRI technology among rice producers in the study area is profitable.

3.3 Determinants of the use of Intensity of System of Rice Intensification

Table 3: Usage intensity of SRI technology

Variables	Seed hill Technology	Transplanting Days (8-12)	Wide spacing	Intermittent weeding	Manure	Transplanting
Experience	0.0468*** (0.007)	0.011*** (0.006)	0.062*** (0.006)	0.021*** (0.009)	-0.034** (0.016)	-0.015*** (0.008)
Association membership	0.205 (0.096)	0.143** (0.085)	0.222 (0.084)	-0.339 (0.123)	-0.020 (0.229)	-0.102 (0.120)
Household size	-0.218** (0.019)	-0.205** (0.016)	-0.017** (0.016)	0.096** (0.024)	-0.364** (0.044)	0.209** (0.023)

Source: Field Survey, 2022

*, ** & *** is significance at 10%, 5% and 1%, respectively.

Education	-0.011*** (0.005)	-0.012*** (0.005)	0.009*** (0.005)	0.015*** (0.007)	-0.037** (0.013)	-0.001*** (0.007)
Extension Services	-0.020*** (0.007)	0.053*** (0.006)	-0.007*** (0.006)	0.049*** (0.009)	-0.032** (0.017)	-0.012*** (0.009)
Constant	4.199 (0.278)	3.436 (0.247)	1.793 (0.244)	0.827 (0.358)	7.527 (0.665)	1.258 (0.350)

Std. Err. in parenthesis

Table 3, showed the result of the multivariate analysis for the determinants of the use of the system of rice intensification (SRI) in the study area. The use of technologies such as Seedhill Technology, Transplanting days, Wide Spacing, Intermittent weeding, Manure, and Transplanting were regressed against socioeconomic variables such as; farming experience, association membership, household size, level of education, and extension services. These results indicate that the use of SRI technology is significantly influenced by certain socioeconomic characteristics in the study area.

Seedhill Technology: The result revealed that farming experience, household size, level of education, and extension service were the significant factors that influence the use of seed hill technology in the study area. The coefficient of rice farming experience is significantly positive at a 1% level, implying that the use of seed hill technology in the study area, increases with the number of years the farmers spent in rice production. The coefficient of household size is significant at 5%, while the level of education and extension service were significant at 1%. The coefficients were all negatively significant to the use of seed hill technology in the study area. This implied that a unit increase in these variables will decrease the use of seed hill technology in the study area by their coefficients.

Transplanting days: The result also showed that the coefficients of farming experience, association membership, household size, level of education, and extension service significantly influenced the use of transplanting technology in the study area. The coefficients of farming experience, association membership, and extension services positively influenced the use of transplanting technology in the study area. This showed that the availability of extension services significantly increases the use of transplanting technology among the rice farming households in the study area, stressing the importance of extension in boosting the use of innovations. This finding is similar to the findings of Asfaw et al. (2012) and Mariano et al. (2012). However, the coefficients of household size and education showed a negative relationship to the use of transplanting technology.

Wide spacing: The result revealed that farming experience, household size, level of education, and extension service significantly influenced the use of wide-spacing technology in the study area. The coefficient of farming experience and education positively influenced the use of wide-spacing technology at a 1% significant level in the study area. According to the findings, the more educated a farmer is, the more likely he or she is to use SRI technology such as wide spacing, presumably due to the fact that he can assimilate relevant data faster than others. This result conforms to previous studies of Langyintuo and Mungoma, (2008), Kassie et al., (2011), and Asfaw et al., (2012). The coefficients of household size and extension service negatively influenced the use of wide-spacing technology in the study area at 1% and 5% significant levels respectively.

Intermittent weeding: Furthermore, the positive and significant signs on farmers' farming experience, household size, level of education, and extension service indicated that they

increased the likelihood of practicing intermittent weeding. This finding is consistent with Ravichandran and Prakash (2015) who found that variables like literacy level, knowledge of farming, knowledge of SRI techniques, and attitude were positively significant with the level of adoption of SRI techniques.

Manure: The results of the analysis also show that farmers' experience, household size, level of education, and extension service were negative and significantly influenced the use of manure in the study area.

Transplanting: The significant factors that influenced the use of transplanting technology among rice farmers were their farming experience, household size, level of education, and extension service. Farming experience, level of education, and extension service negatively influenced the use of transplanting technology. Only the coefficient of household size showed a positive relationship to the use of transplanting technology among rice farmers in the study area.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

The findings showed that most of the rice farmers in Niger State that use SRI technology were male, aged between 31 to 40 years. The profitability index of 0.40 is indicative of the fact that the use of SRI technology in rice farming in the study area is profitable. The result of the multivariate analysis for the determinants of the use of the system of rice intensification (SRI) in the study area revealed that farming experience, household size, level of education, and extension service were the significant variables that influence the use of seed hill technology. The availability of extension services significantly increases the use of transplanting technology among rice farming households in the study area. The coefficient of farming experience and education positively influenced the use of wide-spacing technology at a 1% significant level in the study area. The farmers' farming experience, household size, level of education, and extension service increased their likelihood of practicing intermittent weeding. Farmers' experience, household size, level of education, and extension service were negative and significantly influenced the use of manure in the study area. The coefficient of household size showed a positive relationship to the use of transplanting among rice farmers. Given the importance of extension service and farming experience factors, the study proposes a greater focus on information distribution, extension demonstration, and farmer-collaborative training and research programmes that promote and encourage the use of novel rice varieties. As a result, planners and decision-makers must examine demonstrations at farmers' fields to improve and encourage the usage of SRI Technology.

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